

COMMUNICATIVE FUNCTION OF LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article deals with the issues of the communicative function of the language. Language as the main component of communication.

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Language is the most important means of human communication. It acts as an instrument of communication, thus performing a communicative function. Communicating with each other, people convey their thoughts, expressions of will, feelings and emotional experiences, influence each other in a certain direction, achieve a common understanding. Language gives people the opportunity to understand each other and to work together in all spheres of human activity. Language has been and remains one of the forces that ensure the existence and development of human society. Language as a means of communication is a common property. At the same time, it can perform two social functions - integrating and differentiating.

The language performs these social functions when the historical formation of languages occurs on the basis of the concentration of dialects or the unification of languages, as well as the isolation of the language. The language performs an integrating function when it is used as the language of international or world communication. Such social functions are performed by the Russian language, a language that is not used for communication between peoples, it performs a differentiating function. This is the native language of a particular nation or nationality. The communicative function is one of the main social functions of the language. Knowledge of the language, its categories and units is necessary when learning a language. It is also necessary for language teaching.

In order to use a language, one must master it, i.e. to develop the skills and abilities to speak and read, write and listen to the speech of others. Fluency in a language is based on speech practice, on the transformation of knowledge of language means into skills and abilities to communicate in a particular language in any communication conditions. The presence of communication barriers also characterizes the specifics of interpersonal communication. A communication barrier is a psychological obstacle that arises in the way of transmitting adequate information. In modern social psychology, various types of communication barriers are distinguished. One of them is the barrier of misunderstanding:

phonetic, semantic, stylistic, logical and others. Such barriers arise in connection with various symbolic means of conveying a message.

The simplest example of a phonetic barrier is the misunderstanding of two people speaking different languages. A semantic barrier occurs when people for some reason do not understand the meaning of what was said. An example - a philologist hears a highly professional conversation between two mathematicians. It is unlikely that he will understand what is at stake. The same barrier arises between parents and adolescents if the latter speak in jargon. A semantic barrier can arise between people who are carriers of various subcultures within the dominant culture; they determine the lifestyle and thinking of its carriers. Most often, subcultures of youth, representatives of various professional groups, criminals (delinquent subcultures), children's subcultures, and so on are distinguished. Professional, delinquent and children's subcultures are the most specific in any society. Each subculture has its own specific language, different from others, which can be of great importance not only for the exchange of information in their environment, but also for the way of self-determination and even survival, as happens, for example, in a criminal environment. The stylistic barrier is determined by the difference in the style of presenting information. Styles are usually determined by the functional asymmetry of the human brain as a special phenomenon of the specificity of the left and right hemispheres in relation to various mental functions. The dominance of one of the hemispheres can determine the characteristic difficulties in the perception and processing of information, and the mismatch between the types of dominance of partners leads to the emergence of a stylistic barrier in the process of communication. With the dominance of the logical style, the subject processes and presents information sequentially, without missing a single link from the chain of reasoning. Excessive predilection for details and clarifications does not allow the bearer of the logical style to make decisions quickly, and rationality, coldness and emotional dryness prevent him from establishing contacts with different people. But in situations that are known in advance and do not require new decisions, such people are quite successful.

With the dominance of the expressive style, the subject manifests himself as emotional, impulsive, focused on the opinions of others, capable of empathy and possessing good intuition. Such a person can very easily draw attention to his words and easily establish contact with another. However, excessive exaltation and some scattered thoughts can alienate people with a different style from him. The most optimal is a mixed style, in which there is both a logical vision of the problem and its expressive perception and interpretation. When communicators

disagree about the arguments given, a logical barrier arises. It is inevitable if the interacting parties have different ideas about the essential grounds of judgment. There are also barriers of socio-cultural differences: social, political, religious, professional and others.

Social barriers are determined by the belonging of the subjects of interaction to different social strata of society. Political barriers arise with different ideologies and different ideas about the structure and meaning of power. Religious ones are determined by how tolerant the religion itself is in relation to representatives of another faith. Relationship barriers arise when negative feelings of emotion interfere with an interaction. If the interacting parties experience a feeling of sympathy towards each other, then such barriers do not appear.

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